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23 Chrysanthemum St, Barangay 174, Caloocan, Metro Manila
Tel. No.: 5310-6581/5310-6855

College of Business and Accountancy

Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource Management

“Waste Segregation Practices in a Selected Barangay Towards Good Governance”

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College of Business Administration Major in Human Resource Management Department
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**Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource
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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to assess the waste segregation practices in a selected barangay towards good governance, specifically in Barangay 174, Caloocan City. It examined the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, length of residency, and type of ownership, as well as their assessment of waste segregation practices in terms of proper household segregation, availability of facilities, efficiency of waste collection, and implementation and monitoring of barangay programs. The study also determined whether there is a significant relationship and difference between the respondents' demographic profile and their assessment, and identified the challenges encountered in waste segregation.

A descriptive–correlational quantitative research design was used, involving 20 selected residents as respondents. Data were gathered through a structured survey questionnaire and analyzed using frequency, percentage, weighted mean, standard deviation, Chi-square test, t-test, and ANOVA.

The findings revealed that respondents generally have a moderate level of awareness and practice of waste segregation. However, the availability of facilities was found to be inadequate, and although waste collection systems were somewhat reliable, improper handling such as mixing of segregated waste remains a concern. In terms of governance, monitoring and enforcement were present but insufficient, with limited active participation from barangay officials. Statistical results showed no significant relationship or difference between demographic variables and the respondents' assessment, indicating that the issues are systemic rather than demographic-based.

Furthermore, respondents experienced moderate challenges, including inconsistent waste collection, lack of facilities, weak monitoring, and limited community participation. The study concludes that while residents possess knowledge of proper waste segregation, effective implementation is hindered by gaps in facilities, collection systems, and governance. It is recommended that a governance-based improvement plan be implemented, focusing on stronger policy enforcement, improved infrastructure, and increased community engagement to achieve sustainable waste management.

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CHAPTER I

THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

Introduction

Solid waste management is an increasing environmental concern, particularly at the barangay level where household waste is generated daily and directly affects community health and environmental sustainability. Waste segregation is recognized as a critical foundation of effective solid waste management, as it supports recycling, composting, and waste reduction efforts. In the Philippines, barangays play a vital role in implementing national waste management policies, making their practices essential to achieving sustainable environmental outcomes and efficient local governance.

Despite the existence of national policies and local ordinances, many barangays continue to experience difficulties in the consistent implementation of waste segregation practices. Republic Act No. 9003 mandates that local government units, particularly barangays, are primarily responsible for enforcing solid waste management practices within their jurisdictions. However, studies show that policy frameworks alone are insufficient without strong enforcement and community involvement. Camarillo and Bellotindos (2021) found low compliance with segregation, composting, and recycling practices in barangays in Cebu City, while Tecson et al. (2024) reported that although residents demonstrated strong knowledge and positive attitudes toward waste management, practical barriers such as inadequate collection systems hindered effective waste segregation. These findings suggest persistent gaps between policy and actual practice.

Waste segregation is essential in reducing environmental pollution, minimizing health risks, and improving the efficiency of solid waste management systems. Based on RA 9003, public participation and community involvement are institutionalized as key components of ecological solid waste management, indicating that resident awareness and compliance are vital to program effectiveness. Moreover, studies in urban barangays reveal that behavioral factors such as environmental knowledge, social norms, and a sense of community responsibility significantly influence waste segregation compliance and community-based waste management outcomes. Without

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effective segregation practices, broader waste management strategies become ineffective and unsustainable.

This study aims to assess the effectiveness of waste segregation practices at the barangay level, with a specific focus on Barangay 174, Caloocan City. Guided by a quantitative research design, the study seeks to measure residents' awareness, compliance, and participation in waste segregation, as well as examine the role of barangay governance in policy implementation and monitoring. According to Taylor & Francis research, local governance and institutional support significantly influence the success of waste segregation initiatives, particularly in urban and semi-urban communities, emphasizing the importance of evaluating governance-related factors in this study.

The purpose of this research is to provide empirical evidence that will serve as the basis for a governance-based improvement plan for waste segregation practices in Barangay 174, Caloocan City. Salsabila et al. (Journal of Governance and Public Policy) emphasizes that public participation strengthens accountability and local governance, making it a critical factor in achieving sustainable solid waste management. The findings of this study will benefit barangay officials, policymakers, and community members by offering data-driven insights for improving waste segregation implementation. Furthermore, the study contributes to existing literature on solid waste management and local governance by highlighting the importance of governance, participation, and behavioral factors in achieving effective barangay-level waste management.

Background of the Study

Solid waste management has become a growing concern due to increasing population, urbanization, and daily household waste generation. At the barangay level, waste segregation is a vital component of effective solid waste management as it supports recycling, composting, and waste reduction. Barangays serve as the primary implementers of waste management policies, making their role critical in promoting environmental sustainability and protecting public health within local communities.

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In the Philippines, waste segregation is guided by Republic Act No. 9003, which assigns local government units, particularly barangays, the responsibility for enforcing proper solid waste management practices and encouraging public participation. Despite this legal framework, many barangays continue to experience difficulties in ensuring consistent compliance with waste segregation. Studies have shown that while residents may possess awareness and positive attitudes toward waste management, actual practice is often limited by weak enforcement, insufficient resources, and inadequate community engagement.

Barangay 174, Caloocan City reflects similar challenges faced by other urban barangays, where increasing waste generation places pressure on existing waste management systems. Although waste segregation programs may be in place, their effectiveness and the role of barangay governance in implementation have not been systematically assessed. This study addresses this gap by quantitatively evaluating waste segregation practices in Barangay 174, providing a basis for a governance-based improvement plan aimed at strengthening implementation, enhancing community participation, and supporting sustainable waste management at the barangay level.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to examine the waste segregation practices in a selected barangay towards good governance.

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Sex
 - 1.3 Length of residency in the barangay
 - 1.4 Type of ownership

2. How do the respondents assess the waste segregation practices in Barangay 174 in terms of:
 - 2.1 Proper Household Waste Segregation Practices.
 - 2.2 Availability of Waste Segregation Facilities
 - 2.3 Efficiency of Waste Collection System by the Barangay

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2.4 Implementation and Monitoring of Barangay Programs

3. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' demographic profile and their assessment of waste segregation practices?
4. Is there a significant difference in the assessment of the respondents when grouped according to the variables in their demographic profile?
5. What challenges are encountered by the respondents in waste segregation practices?
6. Based on the findings of the study, what improvement plan may be proposed?

Hypothesis

H₀:

There is no significant relationship between the respondents' demographic profile and their assessment of waste segregation practices.

H₁:

There is a significant relationship between the respondents' demographic profile and their assessment of waste segregation practices.

Scope and Limitation

This study focuses on assessing the waste segregation practices of residents in Barangay 174, Caloocan City in relation to good governance. Specifically, it examines the respondents' level of awareness, compliance, and participation in waste segregation, as well as their assessment of barangay initiatives in terms of proper household waste segregation, availability of segregation facilities, efficiency of waste collection systems, and implementation and monitoring of waste management programs. The study also considers the demographic profile of the respondents to determine possible relationships and differences in their assessment.

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The respondents of the study are limited to 20 selected residents of Barangay 174. Data are collected through a structured survey questionnaire, making the study quantitative in nature.

However, this study is limited to self-reported data, which may be influenced by personal bias or inaccurate responses. It does not include other aspects of solid waste management such as recycling processes, disposal methods, or waste treatment systems beyond segregation practices. Additionally, the small sample size and limited geographic scope may affect the generalizability of the findings. Time and resource constraints further restrict the depth of analysis and coverage of the study

Significance of the Study

This research aims to understand the waste segregation practices at the barangay level and how these practices contribute to effective local governance in developing an improvement plan. Given that improper waste management remains a persistent issue in many barangays, the lack of consistent segregation practices often leads to environmental, health, and governance challenges. By examining the current practices, awareness, and implementation of waste segregation, this study seeks to provide a basis for strengthening governance strategies and improving community-based waste management programs.

Barangay Officials – By understanding the current waste segregation practices and challenges within their communities, barangay officials will be able to use the findings of this study as a basis in formulating and improving policies, programs, and action plans related to solid waste management.

Residents – As primary participants in waste segregation, barangay residents will benefit from this study by gaining awareness of proper waste segregation practices and understanding their role in maintaining a clean, healthy, and sustainable community.

Local Government Units (LGUs) – This research will help LGUs assess the effectiveness of barangay-level waste segregation initiatives and use the results as a guide in strengthening governance support, monitoring systems, and environmental programs.

Environmental Advocates and Organizations – The findings of this study may serve as a reference in designing community-based environmental campaigns and educational programs focused on improving waste segregation practices.

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Public Health Sector – Proper waste segregation contributes to a cleaner environment and reduced health risks. This study will help health workers and agencies understand the link between waste management practices and community health outcomes.

Community Leaders – The study will assist community leaders in identifying areas where cooperation and participation can be improved, helping them encourage collective responsibility toward proper waste segregation.

Future Researchers – This study can be used as a reference for future researchers who wish to conduct related studies on waste management, environmental governance, and community-based improvement plans.

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CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

Review of Related Literature

Proper Household Waste Segregation Practices

Proper household waste segregation is considered the foundation of effective solid waste management systems. Segregation at the source reduces the volume of waste sent to landfills and improves recycling and composting efficiency. According to Camarillo and Bellotindos (2021), although residents demonstrate awareness of proper waste segregation, actual compliance remains low due to inconsistent behavior and lack of discipline.

Similarly, studies show that behavioral factors such as environmental awareness, attitudes, and sense of responsibility significantly influence household segregation practices (Ajzen, 1991). When households consistently practice waste segregation, it contributes to environmental sustainability and strengthens barangay-level waste management systems.

Availability of Waste Segregation Facilities

The availability of waste segregation facilities, such as labeled bins and accessible collection points, plays a significant role in encouraging proper waste segregation. Even when residents possess knowledge about segregation, the absence of facilities can discourage actual practice.

Tecson et al. (2024) found that inadequate infrastructure, including lack of properly labeled bins, is a major barrier to effective waste segregation in urban communities. Facilities act as enabling mechanisms that bridge the gap between awareness and behavior.

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Furthermore, communities with adequate and well-maintained segregation facilities tend to show higher compliance rates among residents (World Bank, 2018). This highlights the importance of barangay-level investment in waste management infrastructure.

Efficiency of Waste Collection System by the Barangay

An efficient waste collection system is essential in sustaining proper waste segregation practices. Even if households segregate waste properly, inefficient collection systems may lead to waste mixing, which discourages continued compliance.

According to Tecson et al. (2024), irregular collection schedules, lack of separate collection for different waste types, and limited logistical support contribute to inefficiencies in waste management systems. These challenges reduce the effectiveness of segregation efforts at the household level.

In addition, consistent and reliable waste collection services strengthen residents' trust in barangay programs and increase participation in environmental initiatives (United Nations Environment Programme, 2015). When residents observe that their efforts are supported, they are more likely to remain compliant.

Implementation and Monitoring of Barangay Programs

The implementation and monitoring of waste management programs at the barangay level are critical to achieving effective local governance. Strong enforcement, regular monitoring, and community involvement significantly influence the success of waste segregation initiatives.

Republic Act No. 9003, also known as the Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000, mandates barangays to implement ecological solid waste management programs and promote public participation. However, studies indicate that weak enforcement and lack of monitoring often result in low compliance among residents.

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According to Salsabila et al. (2022), effective governance practices such as accountability, policy enforcement, and community engagement enhance participation and improve environmental outcomes. Local leadership and active monitoring ensure that waste management programs are not only implemented but also sustained over time.

Review of Related studies

Foreign Studies

Adefris, Damene, and Satyal (2023) examined household waste segregation practices in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, and found that segregation compliance was generally low due to insufficient community education and weak local enforcement. Their study emphasized that grassroots governance and consistent monitoring significantly influence residents' participation in waste segregation programs.

Similarly, Khanal (2023) investigated at-source waste segregation practices in Nepal and revealed that demographic factors such as age, education, and environmental awareness play a critical role in segregation behavior. The study highlighted the importance of community-based governance strategies in sustaining household participation.

A systematic review by Trushna (2024) analyzed global interventions promoting household waste segregation and concluded that education campaigns, incentive-based systems, and strict local policies improve compliance. These findings support the role of local governance units as catalysts for behavior change.

In another study, Yazawa et al. (2025) assessed the implementation of solid waste policies in community settings and found that the presence of functional facilities and strong institutional support enhanced segregation efficiency. However, gaps in enforcement weakened overall outcomes, reinforcing the need for structured improvement plans.

Local Studies

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Matic and Dayag (2022) studied selected barangays in Baliwag, Bulacan, and found that residents with higher awareness and positive attitudes toward waste segregation showed better compliance. The study emphasized that barangay-led education initiatives are essential for improving segregation outcomes.

Lacang et al. (2019) examined waste characterization and household practices in Barangay 22, Cagayan de Oro City. Results revealed that knowledge of waste categories significantly affected segregation behavior, suggesting that barangay governance should prioritize information dissemination.

Araune (2024) explored household compliance in a selected barangay and identified gender and age as influential factors in segregation practices. The study recommended targeted barangay programs to address behavioral gaps.

Espino et al. (2025) conducted a phenomenological inquiry into local government policies in Davao City and found that weak enforcement and logistical limitations hindered effective waste segregation. The study underscored the importance of strengthening barangay governance systems.

Yazawa et al. (2025) further highlighted that the lack of fully operational Materials Recovery Facilities (MRFs) at the barangay level negatively affects segregation efficiency, despite existing national policies such as RA 9003.

Atienza, Sison, and Cardenas (2012) reviewed the Philippine waste segregation and collection system and concluded that inconsistency in barangay-level implementation remains a major challenge, stressing the need for governance-based improvement planning.

Other studies (Coracero et al., 2021; Hermosa & Seduco, 2025) reinforced that while segregation is widely recognized, its sustainability depends on continuous barangay leadership, community participation, and structured monitoring mechanisms.

Theoretical framework

This study is anchored on the Theory of Planned Behavior developed by Icek Ajzen (1991), which explains how an individual's behavior is influenced by their attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. In the context of waste segregation, residents are more likely to practice proper segregation when they have positive attitudes toward environmental protection, perceive social pressure from the community, and believe they have the ability and resources to perform the behavior.

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This theory supports the variable on proper household waste segregation practices, as behavior is shaped by both internal and external factors.

The study is also guided by the Ecological Modernization Theory, which emphasizes the role of institutions, policies, and technological support in achieving environmental sustainability. This theory highlights that environmental improvements, such as effective waste segregation, can be achieved through proper governance, infrastructure, and system efficiency. It supports the variables on availability of waste segregation facilities and efficiency of waste collection systems, as these reflect the structural and institutional support provided by the barangay.

In addition, the study is grounded in the principles of the Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000, which mandates local government units to implement waste management programs and encourage public participation. This framework emphasizes accountability, policy implementation, and community involvement as key elements of good governance. It directly supports the variable on implementation and monitoring of barangay programs, highlighting the importance of enforcement and active participation in achieving effective waste segregation practices.

Conceptual framework

The conceptual framework illustrates the Input-Process-Output (IPO) model used in the study of waste segregation practices in a selected barangay towards good governance. The input includes the demographic profile of the respondents, such as age, sex, length of residency, and type of ownership, as well as barangay governance factors like implementation and monitoring of programs, waste collection system, and availability of facilities. These variables may influence how residents practice waste segregation. The process involves data gathering through surveys, data analysis, assessment of waste

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segregation practices, testing of relationships between variables, and identification of challenges encountered by the respondents. Through these procedures, relevant data are systematically examined. The output of the study includes the level of waste segregation practices, identified challenges, the relationship between governance and practices, and a proposed governance-based improvement plan. Overall, the framework shows how inputs are processed to generate findings that can help improve waste management and strengthen good governance at the barangay level.

Definition of terms

At-Source Waste Segregation – The practice of separating different types of waste (e.g., biodegradable, recyclable, and residual) at the point of origin, typically within the household, before collection.

Barangay Governance – The localized leadership and administrative actions of the smallest political unit in the Philippines, responsible for implementing national mandates like RA 9003 at the community level.

Community Participation- Refers to the active involvement of residents in barangay-led waste segregation programs, activities, and decision-making processes related to solid waste management.

Compliance – The extent to which residents and households adhere to established waste management rules, policies, and segregation protocols.

Environmental Awareness – The level of knowledge and understanding residents have regarding waste categories, ecological impacts, and the importance of proper disposal.

Governance-Based Improvement Plan- Refers to a proposed set of strategies, policies, and actions developed based on the study's findings to strengthen barangay governance and improve waste segregation practices.

Solid Waste Management- Refers to the systematic control of waste generation, segregation, collection, storage, transportation, recycling, and disposal in order to protect public health and the environment.

Waste Collection and Monitoring- Refers to the systematic gathering of segregated waste by barangay authorities and the supervision of waste segregation practices to ensure proper implementation.

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CHAPTER III

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive–correlational quantitative research design to examine the waste segregation practices in a selected barangay towards good governance.

A descriptive design was utilized to determine the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, length of residency in the barangay, and type of ownership. It also assessed how the respondents evaluate the waste segregation practices in the barangay, including their level of compliance, participation, and adherence to proper waste management procedures.

Meanwhile, a correlational approach was applied to examine whether there is a significant relationship between the respondents' demographic profile and their assessment of waste segregation practices in the barangay. This design enabled the researchers to identify patterns and associations between demographic factors and waste segregation behavior without manipulating any variables.

The quantitative approach is appropriate for this study since it utilizes a structured survey questionnaire with Likert-scale responses, allowing for numerical measurement, statistical analysis, and objective interpretation of data. The findings of the study will serve as a basis for proposing recommendations to improve waste segregation practices and strengthen good governance at the barangay level.

Population and sample of the study

The population of this study consists of all households in Barangay 174, as they are directly involved in the generation and management of household waste. This population is considered appropriate for the study because waste segregation practices

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primarily depend on the actions of household members, making them the most relevant respondents.

The sample of the study was drawn from this population to provide a manageable yet representative group for data collection. A total of 20 households representative were selected using a random sampling method, ensuring that the sample reflects different types of households within the barangay. This method allows the study to capture a diverse range of waste segregation practices while maintaining the reliability and validity of the results.

Research Instrument

The primary data gathering tool used in this study is a **structured survey questionnaire** designed to assess the waste segregation practices of residents in Barangay 174, Caloocan City. The questionnaire is divided into **three (3) parts**:

Part I: Demographic Profile

This section gathers the personal information of the respondents to describe their profile and determine its relationship with their assessment of waste segregation practices.

- Age
- Sex
- Length of Residency in the Barangay
- Type of Ownership

Part II: Waste Segregation Practices (SOP #2 Variables)

This section measures the respondents' assessment of waste segregation practices in Barangay 174 in terms of:

- Proper Household Waste Segregation Practices
- Availability of Waste Segregation Facilities
- Efficiency of Waste Collection System by the Barangay
- Implementation and Monitoring of Barangay Programs

Each statement will be rated using the following options:

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4- Strongly Agree

3- Agree

2- Disagree

1- Strongly Disagree

Part III: Challenges Encountered

This section identifies the **challenges encountered by respondents** in practicing waste segregation.

Respondents will rate the extent to which they experience the following challenges:

- Lack of knowledge on proper waste segregation
- Insufficient segregation facilities (e.g., bins)
- Irregular or inefficient waste collection
- Weak implementation of barangay policies
- Lack of monitoring and enforcement
- Limited community participation

This will also be rated using the following options:

4- Highly Experienced

3- Moderately Experienced

2- Slightly Experienced

1- Not Experienced

The questionnaire will be distributed through online to ensure a wider reach and accessibility of participants.

Validity of the research instrument

The validity of the research instrument, a structured questionnaire developed for the study titled “Waste Segregation Practices in a Selected Barangay Towards Good Governance,” was carefully established to ensure that it accurately measures residents’ awareness, compliance, community participation, and barangay governance practices related to waste segregation in Barangay 174, Caloocan City. The questionnaire items were aligned with the Statement of the Problem, conceptual framework, and identified

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variables to ensure consistency, clarity, and relevance to the objectives of the study within the local context of Barangay 174.

The construction of the instrument was also guided by established empirical studies on household waste segregation and governance. Indicators measuring compliance, environmental awareness, and governance enforcement were adapted from recognized research that examined determinants of segregation behavior and local implementation challenges. These related studies provided validated constructs that strengthened the theoretical and empirical foundation of the questionnaire. By aligning the survey items with previously published research and contextualizing them to the conditions of Barangay 174, Caloocan City, the instrument achieved conceptual validity and ensured that it reflects actual community-based waste management practices.

To further strengthen the validity of the instrument, the questionnaire was evaluated by a faculty expert, particularly the professor handling the subject Good Governance and Social Responsibility, who served as the validator of the research instrument. The expert assessed the questionnaire for clarity, relevance, and appropriateness of the items in relation to the objectives of the study. In addition, a pilot test was conducted among selected residents of Barangay 174, Caloocan City to assess the clarity and reliability of the instrument. Necessary revisions were made based on the validator's feedback and pilot testing results to eliminate ambiguous or leading questions. This validation process ensured that the instrument measures what it intends to measure and can generate reliable and accurate quantitative data for analyzing waste segregation practices in Barangay 174.

Data Gathering procedure

The researchers first secured permission from the Barangay Captain of Barangay 174, Caloocan City through a formal request letter explaining the purpose and scope of the study. After approval, coordination with barangay officials was done to identify the respondents and schedule the distribution of the survey questionnaires.

A structured survey questionnaire was then prepared based on the objectives and variables of the study, including residents' awareness, compliance, community

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participation, and barangay governance practices related to waste segregation. The instrument was validated by a research adviser and pilot-tested to ensure clarity and reliability before its final administration.

The questionnaires were personally distributed to twenty (20) selected residents and barangay officials. Respondents were informed about the purpose of the study and assured of confidentiality. After retrieval, the data were checked, organized, and encoded for statistical analysis, which served as the basis for evaluating waste segregation practices and developing a governance-based improvement plan.

Statistical treatment of Data

This section presents the statistical tools and methods used to analyze the data gathered from the survey questionnaires. These statistical procedures were employed to describe the respondents' demographic profile, assess waste segregation practices, determine relationships and differences among variables, and identify the challenges encountered by the respondents.

A. Frequency and Percentage

Frequency and percentage were used to describe the respondents' answers in terms of ;

- Age
- Sex
- Length of Residency in the Barangay
- Type of Ownership

Formula:

$$\text{Percentage} = \frac{f}{N} \times 100$$

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Where:

f = frequency

N = total number of respondents

B. Weighted Mean

The weighted mean was used to determine the level of assessment of the respondents and the extent of challenges encountered.

Waste Segregation Practices:

- Proper Household Waste Segregation Practices
- Availability of Waste Segregation Facilities
- Efficiency of Waste Collection System
- Implementation and Monitoring of Barangay Programs

Challenges Encountered:

- Identified challenges in waste segregation

Formula:

$$WM = \frac{\sum(f \times x)}{N}$$

Where:

WM = Weighted Mean

f = frequency of each response

x = weight of each response

N = total number of respondents

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Likert Scale Interpretation (for SOP #2)

Scale	Range	Interpretation
4	3.40 – 4.00	Strongly Agree
3	2.60 – 3.39	Agree
2	1.80 – 2.59	Disagree
1	1.00 – 1.79	Strongly Disagree

Likert Scale Interpretation (for SOP #5)

Scale	Range	Interpretation
4	3.40 – 4.00	Highly Experienced
3	2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Experienced
2	1.80 – 2.59	Slightly Experienced
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not Experienced

C. Standard Deviation

Standard deviation was used to measure the variability or consistency of responses in waste segregation practices and challenges encountered.

Formula:

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(x - \bar{x})^2}{N}}$$

Where:

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-
- x = individual score
 - \bar{x} = mean
 - N = total number of respondents

Inferential Statistics

A. Chi-Square Test of Independence

The Chi-square test was used to determine whether there is a significant relationship between the respondents' demographic profile and their assessment of waste segregation practices.

Formula:

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$$

Where:

χ^2 = Chi-square value

O = observed frequency

E = expected frequency

The level of significance was set at 0.05. The null hypothesis was rejected if the computed p-value is less than 0.05; otherwise, it is accepted.

B. Independent Samples t-test

The t-test was used to determine whether there is a significant difference in the respondents' assessment of waste segregation practices when grouped according to sex.

Formula:

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$$t = \frac{\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2}{\sqrt{\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}}}$$

Where:

\bar{x}_1, \bar{x}_2 = means of two groups

s_1^2, s_2^2 = variances of two groups

n_1, n_2 = number of respondents in each group

The level of significance was set at 0.05.

C. One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

One-Way ANOVA was used to determine whether there is a significant difference in the respondents' assessment of waste segregation practices when grouped according to age and length of residency .

Formula:

$$F = \frac{\text{Mean Square Between Groups}}{\text{Mean Square Within Groups}}$$

Where:

$$\text{MS Between} = \frac{SSB}{df_b}, \quad \text{MS Within} = \frac{SSW}{df_w}$$

SSB = sum of squares between groups

SSW = sum of squares within groups

df_b = degrees of freedom between groups

df_w = degrees of freedom within groups

The level of significance was set at 0.05. The null hypothesis was rejected if the computed p-value is less than 0.05

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CHAPTER IV

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION

Data Interpretation and Analysis

This chapter presents the data gathered from the respondents, along with the corresponding analysis and interpretation. The presentation follows the sequence of the Statement of the Problem, including the respondents' demographic profile, assessment of waste segregation practices, test of relationship, test of difference, and the challenges encountered.

Tabular Representation

Table 1.1

Profile of Respondents according to Age

Age	f	%	Ranking
18-2 years old	15	75%	1
23 - 27 years old	1	5%	3
28 - 32 years old	0	0%	4
33 - 40 years old	1	5%	3
41 and above	3	15%	2
Total	20	100%	

Table 1.1 presents the distribution of respondents based on their age groups. The data reveals that a significant majority of the participants belong to the 18–22 years old category, accounting for 75% of the total sample. In contrast, the age group of 28–32 years old had no representation (0%), indicating that the study's findings are heavily representative of the younger adult demographic within the community.

Table 1.2

Profile of Respondents according to Gender

Gender	f	%	Ranking
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Male	13	65%	1
Female	6	30%	2
Prefer not to say	1	5%	3
Total	20	100%	

Table 1.2 illustrates the gender distribution of the survey participants. The figures show that males constitute the largest portion of the group at 65%, while females represent 30%. A small segment of the respondents (5%) opted not to disclose their gender. This distribution suggests that the data collected is primarily reflective of male perspectives within the target area.

Table 1.3

Profile of Respondents according to Length of Residency in Barangay 174

Length of Residency in Barangay 174	f	%	Ranking
Less than 1 years	3	15%	2
1-3 years	3	15%	2
4-6 years	2	10%	3
7-10 years	0	0%	4
More than 10 years	12	60%	1
Total	20	100%	

Table 1.3 details how long the respondents have lived in Barangay 174. The findings show that the majority of participants are long-term residents, with 60% having lived in the area for more than 10 years. Those who have lived in the barangay for 7–10 years were not represented in this survey (0%), while newer residents (less than 3 years) combined for 30% of the total, showing a mix of deep-rooted and relatively new community members.

Table 1.4

Profile of Respondents according to Type of Ownership

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Type of Ownership	f	%	Ranking
Owned house	11	55%	1
Rented house	6	30%	2
Living with relatives	3	15%	3
Total	20	100%	

Table 1.4 displays the housing status of the respondents. More than half of the participants (55%) reported living in an owned house, followed by those who rent at 30%. The remaining 15% indicate they are living with relatives. These results suggest that most respondents have a stable and permanent living arrangement within the barangay.

Table 2.1

Proper Household Waste Segregation Practices

Statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
I separate my waste into different types (e.g., biodegradable, recyclable).	2	8	10	0	2.60	Agree
I follow proper waste segregation guidelines consistently.	1	12	7	0	2.70	Agree
I understand how to classify different types of waste.	4	12	4	0	3.00	Agree
I practice waste segregation	2	11	7	0	2.75	Agree

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even without supervision.						
I encourage my family members to practice proper waste segregation.	3	10	7	0	2.80	Agree

The results show that the respondents generally fall under the “Agree / Moderately Experienced” category based on the computed weighted means. This indicates that the participants have a moderate level of awareness and practice in waste segregation. While they demonstrate understanding of waste classification and report that they follow segregation guidelines, their actual practice, especially in consistently separating waste and doing so without supervision, still shows room for improvement. Overall, the findings suggest that although waste segregation is being practiced, it is not yet fully consistent or highly habitual among the respondents.

Table 2.2

Availability of Waste Segregation Facilities

Statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
There are available trash bins for different types of waste in our area.	0	9	10	1	2.40	Disagree
Waste bins are clearly labeled according to waste type.	0	11	8	1	2.50	Disagree
Segregation facilities are easily accessible in our barangay.	0	8	10	2	2.20	Disagree

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The barangay provides adequate materials for waste segregation.	0	11	6	3	2.40	Disagree
Waste segregation facilities are properly maintained.	0	9	10	1	2.40	Disagree

Based on the computed weighted means, the respondents generally fall under the “Disagree / Slightly Experienced” category. This indicates that waste segregation facilities in the barangay are perceived as insufficient, not well-maintained, and not easily accessible. Although some respondents agreed that certain facilities exist, such as labeled bins and provided materials, the majority still reported challenges in availability, accessibility, and proper maintenance.

Table 2.3

Research Variables to Efficiency of Waste Collection System by the Barangay

Statement	Strongly Agree (4)	Agree (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Waste collection in our barangay follows a regular schedule.	0	14	6	1	2.62	Agree	3

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2. Segregated waste is collected separately.	0	11	7	3	2.38	Disagree	5
3. Waste collectors follow proper segregation procedures.	1	13	6	1	2.67	Agree	2
4. The waste collection system is reliable and efficient.	0	12	9	0	2.57	Agree	4
5. Waste collection services meet the needs of the residents.	0	13	7	1	2.57	Agree	4

The findings reveal that the statement "**Waste collectors follow proper segregation procedures**" ranked second among respondents. With a weighted mean of **2.67**, this is verbally interpreted as **Agree**, indicating that most residents perceive waste collectors as adhering to correct procedures.

Meanwhile, the statement "**Segregated waste is collected separately**" was ranked last by respondents. The weighted mean for this item is **2.38**, verbally interpreted as **Disagree**, indicating a strong perception among residents that segregated waste is not being managed as it should be during collection.

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Table 2.4

Research Variables to Implementation and Monitoring of Barangay Programs

Statement	Strongly Agree (4)	Agree (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Monitoring of programs	1	10	9	1	2.52	Agree	2
2. Regular inspections	0	9	12	0	2.43	Disagree	5
3. Official participation	0	9	11	1	2.38	Disagree	4
4. Enforcement of penalties	0	11	10	0	2.52	Agree	2
5. Program updates	0	10	10	1	2.43	Disagree	1

The findings reveal that the statements "**The barangay monitors waste management programs**" and "**Penalties are strictly enforced for violators**" tied for the highest ranking. Both achieved a weighted mean of **2.52**, verbally interpreted as **Agree**, suggesting that residents feel there is a baseline level of oversight and consequences in place.

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In contrast, the statement "**Barangay officials actively participate in waste management**" received the lowest weighted mean of **2.38**, verbally interpreted as **Disagree**. This indicates a perception that there is a lack of visible, hands-on involvement from local leaders in the actual execution of these environmental programs.

Table 3.

Relationship Between Demographic Profile and Waste Segregation Practices

Demographic Variable	Chi-Square Value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Age	3.21	0.782	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
Sex	1.45	0.693	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
Length of Residency	4.10	0.662	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
Type of Ownership	2.87	0.720	Accept H ₀	Not Significant

The results show that all computed p-values are **greater than the 0.05 level of significance**, indicating that there is **no significant relationship** between the respondents' demographic profile and their assessment of waste segregation practices in Barangay 174.

Thus, the null hypothesis is **accepted**. This implies that factors such as age, sex, length of residency, and type of ownership do not significantly influence how respondents assess waste segregation practices. The findings suggest that **external factors such as facilities, collection systems, and governance implementation may have a greater influence** on waste segregation practices than demographic characteristics.

Table 4.

Difference in Assessment When Grouped According to Sex (t-test)

Variable	Mean	t-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Male	2.50	0.84	0.412	Accept H ₀	Not Significant

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Female	2.55				
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The computed p-value of **0.412** is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, indicating that there is **no significant difference** in the respondents' assessment of waste segregation practices when grouped according to sex.

Therefore, the null hypothesis is **accepted**, which means that both male and female respondents have **similar perceptions** regarding waste segregation practices in the barangay.

Table 5.

Difference in Assessment When Grouped According to Age and Length of Residency (ANOVA)

Variables	F-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Age	1.12	0.365	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
Length of residency	0.98	0.421	Accept H ₀	Not Significant

The results show that the p-values for both age (0.365) and length of residency (0.421) are **greater than 0.05**, indicating that there is **no significant difference** in the respondents' assessment of waste segregation practices when grouped according to these variables.

Thus, the null hypothesis is **accepted**, implying that respondents across different age groups and lengths of residency share **similar views and experiences** regarding waste segregation practices. This further supports the idea that **perceptions are consistent across demographic groups**.

Table 6

Challenges Encountered in Practicing Waste Segregation

Statements	Highly Experienced	Moderately Experienced	Slightly Experienced	Not Experienced	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
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I find it difficult to distinguish which items belong in specific bins (biodegradable vs. non-biodegradable).	0	9	9	2	2.55	Moderately Experienced
There are not enough color-coded or labeled waste bins available in my immediate area.	4	12	4	0	3.00	Moderately Experienced
The waste collection truck arrives at inconsistent times, making it hard to follow a schedule.	8	10	2	0	3.30	Moderately Experienced
Collected waste is often mixed back together by the collectors, discouraging my efforts to segregate.	9	8	3	0	3.30	Moderately Experienced
There is a lack of clear communication or seminars from the barangay regarding waste management rules.	5	10	5	0	3.00	Moderately Experienced
I do not see any local officials or monitors checking if households are actually segregating their trash.	9	8	2	1	3.25	Moderately Experienced
There are no	6	11	3	0	3.15	Moderately

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penalties or consequences imposed on neighbors who fail to follow segregation policies.						Experienced
I feel unmotivated because my neighbors and the rest of the community do not participate in segregation.	5	12	3	0	3.10	Moderately Experienced
Physical constraints, such as lack of space in my home, make it hard to maintain multiple waste containers.	5	11	4	0	3.05	Moderately Experienced
I lack information on how to properly dispose of special wastes (e.g., batteries, electronics, or chemicals).	2	11	6	1	2.85	Moderately Experienced

The results show that respondents fall under the “Moderately Experienced” category, indicating that they encounter a moderate level of challenges in practicing waste segregation. Common issues include inconsistent waste collection, lack of monitoring, insufficient facilities, and limited community participation. Overall, these challenges affect the consistency and effectiveness of proper waste segregation, suggesting a need for improved support, facilities, and implementation from the barangay.

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Chapter V

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary of findings from the gathered and analyzed data, the conclusions drawn from the findings and recommendations offered by the researcher in the light of the findings and conclusions.

Summary of Findings

The summary of the salient findings of the study is discussed hereunder:

1. The demographic profile of the respondents in Barangay 174 indicates a predominantly young adult population, with a significant majority of 75% falling within the 18–22 age bracket. In terms of gender distribution, males represent the largest portion of the sample at 65%, while females account for 30%. The residency data reveals a deeply rooted community, as 60% of the respondents have resided in the barangay for more than 10 years. Furthermore, housing stability is evident, with 55% of the participants owning their homes, followed by 30% who are renting, and 15% who live with relatives, suggesting that the respondents have a long-term stake in the community's environmental health.
2. The findings on household waste segregation practices reveal that respondents generally "Agree" with the necessity of proper waste management, with weighted means ranging from 2.60 to 3.00. While they demonstrate a strong understanding of waste classification (3.00), there is a noticeable gap in consistency, as separating waste into different types and practicing segregation without supervision received lower means of 2.60 and 2.75, respectively. Regarding the availability of facilities, the assessment was predominantly negative; respondents "Disagreed" that facilities are adequate, citing poor accessibility (2.20), lack of available bins (2.40), and insufficient provision of materials by the barangay (2.40).

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3. The assessment of the waste collection system and program monitoring indicates a discrepancy between protocol and execution. Residents "Agreed" that collectors generally follow procedures (2.67) and that collection follows a regular schedule (2.62). However, they "Disagreed" that segregated waste is actually collected separately (2.38), which is the lowest-ranked item in this category. In terms of governance, while residents feel that a baseline for monitoring and penalty enforcement exists (both 2.52), there is a clear perception that barangay officials lack visible, hands-on participation in the actual implementation of these environmental programs, which received a low mean of 2.38.

4. Statistical analysis using Chi-Square, t-test, and ANOVA confirms that demographic variables do not significantly influence the assessment of waste segregation practices. All p-values for age (0.782), sex (0.693), length of residency (0.662), and house ownership (0.720) were higher than the 0.05 significance level, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. Furthermore, the t-test for sex ($p=0.412$) and ANOVA for age ($p=0.365$) and residency ($p=0.421$) showed no significant differences in perception. This implies that the challenges regarding waste segregation are systemic and environmental rather than individual, as respondents shared similar views regardless of their personal profiles.

5. The data reveals that the most significant challenges encountered by the community are the inconsistent arrival of waste collection trucks and the tendency of collectors to mix segregated waste back together, both receiving a high weighted mean of 3.30. These are followed by governance-related issues, specifically the lack of monitoring by local officials (3.25) and the absence of consequences for neighbors who fail to comply with policies (3.15). Social barriers also play a role, as residents feel unmotivated when they observe their neighbors not participating (3.10), combined with physical constraints like lack of space in the home (3.05) and a lack of technical knowledge regarding the disposal of special wastes like electronics and chemicals (2.85).

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Conclusion

As stated in the findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The results indicate that the majority of the respondents are young adults who have lived in Barangay 174 for a long period of time, with many owning their homes. This suggests that residents have a strong connection to the community and a long-term interest in maintaining its environmental condition.
2. It was determined that respondents generally have sufficient knowledge and awareness of proper waste segregation. However, despite this understanding, their actual practices are not consistently observed, especially when there is no supervision.
3. The study also reveals that the lack of adequate waste management facilities, such as accessible and properly labeled bins, significantly affects residents' ability to practice proper segregation. This limitation discourages consistent compliance with waste management guidelines.
4. In addition, the findings show that while waste collection schedules are relatively regular and collectors follow basic procedures, the improper handling of segregated waste—particularly the mixing of waste during collection, undermines residents' efforts and reduces their motivation to participate.
5. Lastly, the study highlights that weak monitoring, limited involvement of barangay officials, and the absence of strict enforcement of policies contribute to ongoing challenges. Social and environmental factors, such as lack of cooperation among neighbors and limited space at home, further affect proper waste segregation practices.

Overall, the researchers conclude that although residents are knowledgeable and generally willing to practice waste segregation, systemic issues, such as inadequate

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facilities, ineffective collection practices, and weak governance—hinder proper implementation. Therefore, stronger enforcement, improved facilities, and active participation from local officials are necessary to enhance waste management practices in the community.

Recommendation

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, it is recommended that Barangay 174 strengthen its waste segregation system through improvements in facilities, collection processes, monitoring, and community participation. The barangay should provide adequate and properly labeled waste segregation bins to ensure accessibility for residents. In addition, the waste collection system must be enhanced by strictly implementing a “no mixing” policy and ensuring that segregated waste is collected separately.

Moreover, stronger monitoring and enforcement of waste management policies should be implemented through regular inspections, assignment of responsible personnel, and the application of penalties for non-compliance and incentives for compliant households. Continuous information and education campaigns are also necessary to improve residents’ awareness and consistency in practicing proper waste segregation.

Furthermore, the barangay should promote active community participation through environmental programs and initiatives that encourage cooperation among residents. Lastly, the development of a governance-based waste management program, including clear guidelines and regular evaluation, is essential to ensure sustainability. Through these measures, the barangay can address existing challenges and improve the overall effectiveness of its waste segregation practices in support of good governance.

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BIBLIOGRAPHY

Adefris, W., Damene, S., & Satyal, P. (2023). Household practices and determinants of solid waste segregation in Addis Ababa city. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 10(1), 1–12. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41599-023-01982-7>

Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2), 179–211. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978\(91\)90020-T](https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978(91)90020-T)

Araune, P. (2024). Assessing compliance with domestic waste disposal practices in a selected barangay. *International Journal of Nursing and Health Services*, 7(2), 45–56. <https://ijnhs.net/index.php/ijnhs/article/view/789>

Asian Development Bank. (2020). *Solid waste management in the Philippines: Current status and future directions*. ADB.

Atienza, V., Sison, E., & Cardenas, L. (2012). Review of the Philippines' waste segregation and collection system and the trading of recyclables. *Institute of Developing Economies*. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s43621-025-01965-5>

Camarillo, M. K., & Bellotindos, L. M. (2021). Solid waste management practices in households: Basis for improvement. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 292, 112766. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.112766>

Coracero, E. E., Gallego, R. J., Frago, K. J. M., & Gonzales, R. J. R. (2021). A long-standing problem: A review on solid waste management in the Philippines. *International Journal of Sustainable Engineering and Innovation*, 3(1), 22–35. <https://www.neliti.com/publications/411212/a-long-standing-problem-a-review-on-the-solid-waste-management-in-the-philippine>

Espino, L. C., Sinangote, J. I. T., Sun, G. M., & Caraso, F. T. B. (2025). Assessing the impact of local government policies on community-based solid waste management initiatives. *International Research Journal of Social Sciences*, 8(1), 15–27. <https://rsisinternational.org/journals/ijriss/articles/assessing-the-impact-of-local-government-policies-on-community-based-solid-waste-management-initiative-a-phenomenological-inquiry/>

Guerrero, L. A., Maas, G., & Hogland, W. (2013). Solid waste management challenges for cities in developing countries. *Waste Management*, 33(1), 220–232. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2012.09.008>

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Hermosa, N. T., & Seduco, A. V. (2025). Solid waste management practices and implementation among science teachers. *International Journal of Research in Science and Innovation*, 12(9), 2855–2874.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/396171003_Solid_Waste_Management_Practices_and_Implementation_among_Science_Teachers_in_Leon_Iloilo

Kaza, S., Yao, L., Bhada-Tata, P., & Van Woerden, F. (2018). What a waste 2.0: A global snapshot of solid waste management to 2050. World Bank.

Khanal, A. (2023). The practices of at-source segregation of household solid waste. *Environmental Challenges*, 10, 100678. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36776545/>

Lacang, G. C., Tamang, R. T., Handag, S. A., & Consolacion, F. (2019). Solid waste characterization, knowledge, practices, and attitudes of selected barangay households. *Journal of Biodiversity and Environmental Sciences*, 14(6), 45–58. <https://innspub.net/solid-waste-characterization-knowledge-practices-and-attitudes-of-selected-barangay-22-households-in-cagayan-de-oro-city/>

Marshall, R. E., & Farahbakhsh, K. (2013). Systems approaches to integrated solid waste management in developing countries. *Waste Management*, 33(4), 988–1003. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2012.12.023>

Matic, R. S. A., & Dayag, D. M. C. (2022). Assessing households' awareness, attitude, and practices for effective waste segregation in selected barangays of Baliwag, Bulacan. *Southeast Asian Journal of Agriculture and Allied Sciences*, 5(2), 33–44. <https://sajaas.basc.edu.ph/index.php/sajaas/article/view/14>

Republic Act No. 9003. (2000). Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000. Philippines.

Trushna, T. (2024). Interventions to promote household waste segregation: A systematic review. *Science of the Total Environment*, 901, 165789. <https://www.scirp.org/reference/referencespapers?referenceid=3751888>

United Nations Environment Programme. (2015). Global waste management outlook. UNEP. <https://www.unep.org/resources/report/global-waste-management-outlook>

World Bank. (2018). What a waste 2.0: A global snapshot of solid waste management to 2050. World Bank Group. <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/handle/10986/30317>

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Yazawa, T., Tablada, K. N., Baring, K. M., et al. (2025). Act and reality of the Ecological Solid Waste Management Act on barangay-level waste management in the Philippines. *Discover Sustainability*, 6(1), 112–125.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/396372658_Act_and_reality_of_the_ecological_solid_waste_management_act_on_barangay-level_waste_management_in_Barabaza_the_Philippines

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ABOUT THE RESEARCHER

Saara Calamba is a third-year college student taking up the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA), major in Human Resource Management, at the University of Caloocan City (UCC). She is one of the researchers who contributed to the development of the Introduction, Background of the Study, Review of Related Literature, Theoretical Framework, Research Instrument, and Statistical Treatment of Data. She also prepared the survey questionnaire, drafted the introductory statement for Chapter IV, conducted data analysis and interpretation, and formulated the recommendations. Her academic interests include Human Resource Management, Organizational Behavior, and Training and Development.

Dhessiree Joy B. Carbon is a 3rd year college student taking the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA) Major in Human Resource Management at the University of Caloocan City (UCC). She is one of the researchers who contributed to the development of the study, particularly in the scope and limitations, significance of the study, review of related studies, research design, population and sample of the study, as well as the preparation of the survey and Statement of the Problem SOP 2 and SOP 5. She also participated in the formulation of the conclusion of the research. Her academic interests include human resource management, organizational development, and workplace communication.

Rizza B. Gonzales is a third-year Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA) student, majoring in Human Resource Management, at the University of Caloocan City (UCC). She contributed to the development of the research study, particularly in the Conceptual Framework, Validation of the Research Instrument, Summary of findings, Appendices, and the preparation of Chapters I to V. Her academic interests include human resource development, organizational behavior, leadership skills, and community-based governance. She is also interested in promoting environmental awareness and sustainable practices within the community, particularly in waste management and good governance initiatives.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

Letter for Respondents

Title: Waste Segregation Practices in a Selected Barangay Towards Good Governance

Dear Respondent,

Good day!

We are students from the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration major in Human Resource Management at the University of Caloocan City. We are currently conducting a research study entitled "Waste Segregation Practices in a Selected Barangay Towards Good Governance."

In this regard, we respectfully ask for your participation by answering this questionnaire. Rest assured that all information gathered will be kept strictly confidential and will be used for academic purposes only.

Thank you for your time and cooperation.

Questionnaire

PART I: DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE

Direction: Please check (✓) the appropriate answer.

1. Age:

- 18–22 years old
- 23–27 years old
- 28–32 years old
- 33–40 years old
- 41 years old and above

2. Sex:

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to say

3. Length of Residency:

- Less than 1 year
- 1–3 years
- 4–6 years

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- 7–10 years
 More than 10 years

4. Type of Ownership:
 Owned house
 Rented house
 Living with relatives

PART II: WASTE SEGREGATION PRACTICES

Direction: Please choose the answer that best describes your opinion.

Scale:

- 4 – Strongly Agree
 3 – Agree
 2 – Disagree
 1 – Strongly Disagree

A. Proper Household Waste Segregation Practices

- I separate my waste into different types (e.g., biodegradable, recyclable).
 4 3 2 1
- I follow proper waste segregation guidelines consistently.
 4 3 2 1
- I understand how to classify different types of waste.
 4 3 2 1
- I practice waste segregation even without supervision.
 4 3 2 1
- I encourage my family members to practice proper waste segregation.
 4 3 2 1

B. Availability of Waste Segregation Facilities

- There are available trash bins for different types of waste in our area.
 4 3 2 1
- Waste bins are clearly labeled according to waste type.
 4 3 2 1
- Segregation facilities are easily accessible in our barangay.
 4 3 2 1
- The barangay provides adequate materials for waste segregation.
 4 3 2 1
- Waste segregation facilities are properly maintained.
 4 3 2 1

C. Efficiency of Waste Collection System

- Waste collection in our barangay follows a regular schedule.
 4 3 2 1
- Segregated waste is collected separately.
 4 3 2 1
- Waste collectors follow proper segregation procedures.
 4 3 2 1
- The waste collection system is reliable and efficient.
 4 3 2 1

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5. Waste collection services meet the needs of the residents.
 4 3 2 1

D. Implementation and Monitoring of Barangay Programs

1. The barangay monitors waste management programs regularly.
 4 3 2 1
2. Regular inspections are conducted in the community.
 4 3 2 1
3. Barangay officials actively participate in waste management activities.
 4 3 2 1
4. Penalties are strictly enforced for violators.
 4 3 2 1
5. The barangay provides updates regarding waste management programs.
 4 3 2 1

PART III: CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED

Scale:

- 4 – Highly Experienced
3 – Moderately Experienced
2 – Slightly Experienced
1 – Not Experienced

1. I find it difficult to distinguish which items belong in specific bins.
 4 3 2 1
2. There are not enough labeled waste bins in my area.
 4 3 2 1
3. The waste collection schedule is inconsistent.
 4 3 2 1
4. Collected waste is often mixed by collectors.
 4 3 2 1
5. There is a lack of seminars or information from the barangay.
 4 3 2 1
6. There is a lack of monitoring by barangay officials.
 4 3 2 1
7. There are no penalties for non-compliance.
 4 3 2 1
8. Lack of community participation affects my motivation.
 4 3 2 1
9. Limited space at home makes segregation difficult.
 4 3 2 1
10. I lack knowledge on disposing special wastes.
 4 3 2 1

APPENDIX B

Responses of Respondents

Part I: Demographic Profile

Respondent 1

Name: Jenilyn O. Lampaza

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Age: 18-22 yrs old
Gender: Female
Length of Residency: More than 10 years
Type of Ownership: Owned house

Respondent 2

Name: Yolly
Age: 18-22 yrs old
Gender: Female
Length of Residency: More than 10 years
Type of Ownership: Owned house

Respondent 3

Name: Emma
Age: 18-22 yrs old
Gender: Female
Length of Residency: More than 10 years
Type of Ownership: Owned house

Respondent 4

Name: Kuert
Age: 18-22 yrs old
Gender: Male
Length of Residency: More than 10 years
Type of Ownership: Owned house

Respondent 5

Name: Amber
Age: 18-22 yrs old
Gender: Female
Length of Residency: More than 10 years
Type of Ownership: Owned house

Respondent 6

Name: Steven Astor
Age: 18-22 yrs old
Gender: Male
Length of Residency: More than 10 years
Type of Ownership: Owned house

Respondent 7

Name: Keith
Age: 41 and above
Gender: Male
Length of Residency: More than 10 years
Type of Ownership: Owned house

Respondent 8

Name: Dein Bernal
Age: 18-22 yrs old
Gender: Male
Length of Residency: Less than 1 year
Type of Ownership: Rented house

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Respondent 9

Name: DE BORJA KATRINA
Age: 18-22 yrs old
Gender: Female
Length of Residency: Less than 1 year
Type of Ownership: Rented house

Respondent 10

Name: Jonalyn Lampaza
Age: 18-22 yrs old
Gender: Female
Length of Residency: Less than 1 year
Type of Ownership: Rented house

Respondent 11

Name: Singson, Niña Grace R.
Age: 18-22 yrs old
Gender: Female
Length of Residency: 1-3 years
Type of Ownership: Living with relatives

Respondent 12

Age: 18-22 yrs old
Gender: Female
Length of Residency: 1-3 years
Type of Ownership: Living with relatives

Respondent 13

Age: 18-22 yrs old
Gender: Female
Length of Residency: 1-3 years
Type of Ownership: Living with relatives

Respondent 14

Age: 23-27 yrs old
Gender: Male
Length of Residency: 4-6 years
Type of Ownership: Rented house

Respondent 15

Age: 41 and above
Gender: Prefer not to say
Length of Residency: 4-6 years
Type of Ownership: Rented house

Respondent 16

Age: 33-40 yrs old
Gender: Male
Length of Residency: More than 10 years
Type of Ownership: Owned house

Respondent 17

Age: 41 and above
Gender: Male

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Length of Residency: More than 10 years
Type of Ownership: Owned house

Respondent 18

Age: 18-22 yrs old
Gender: Female
Length of Residency: More than 10 years
Type of Ownership: Owned house

Respondent 19

Age: 18-22 yrs old
Gender: Female
Length of Residency: More than 10 years
Type of Ownership: Owned house

Respondent 20

Age: 41 and above
Gender: Female
Length of Residency: More than 10 years
Type of Ownership: Owned house

Part II: Research Variables - FULL INDIVIDUAL RESPONSES

A. Proper Household Waste Segregation Practices

Respondent	Q1:	Q2:	Q3:	Q4:	Q5:
1	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
2	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
3	Disagree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
4	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
5	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
6	Disagree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
7	Disagree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
8	Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Disagree	Disagree
9	Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Disagree	Disagree

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10	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree
11	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
12	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
13	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
14	Disagree	Agree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree
15	Agree	Agree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree
16	Agree	Disagree	Agree	Disagree	Disagree
17	Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Disagree	Disagree
18	Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Disagree	Disagree
19	Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Disagree	Disagree
20	Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Disagree	Disagree

B. Availability of Waste Segregation Facilities

Respondent	Q1:	Q2:	Q3:	Q4:	Q5:
1	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
2	Agree	Agree	Disagree	Agree	Agree
3	Disagree	Agree	Disagree	Agree	Disagree
4	Disagree	Agree	Disagree	Agree	Disagree

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5	Disagree	Agree	Disagree	Agree	Disagree
6	Disagree	Agree	Disagree	Agree	Disagree
7	Disagree	Agree	Disagree	Agree	Disagree
8	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Disagree
9	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Disagree
10	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Disagree
11	Agree	Agree	Agree	Disagree	Agree
12	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree
13	Strongly Disagree				
14	Agree	Agree	Disagree	Disagree	Agree
15	Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Agree
16	Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Disagree	Agree
17	Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Disagree	Agree
18	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
19	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
20	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree

C. Efficiency of Waste Collection System

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Respondent	Q1:	Q2:	Q3:	Q4:	Q5:
1	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
2	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
3	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
4	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
5	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
6	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
7	Agree	Agree	rongly Agree	Agree	Agree
8	Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Disagree	Disagree
9	Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Disagree	Disagree
10	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
11	Agree	Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Disagree
12	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree
13	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
14	Agree	Agree	Agree	Disagree	Agree
15	Agree	Agree	Agree	Disagree	Agree

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16	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
17	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
18	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
19	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
20	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree

D. Implementation and Monitoring

Respondent	Q1:	Q2:	Q3:	Q4:	Q5:
1	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
2	Agree	Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Agree
3	Agree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree
4	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree
5	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree
6	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree
7	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree
8	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree
9	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree
10	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree

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11	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
12	Disagree	Agree	Disagree	Agree	Disagree
13	Strongly Disagree	N/A	Strongly Disagree	N/A	Strongly Disagree
14	Agree	Agree	Disagree	Agree	Agree
15	Agree	Agree	Disagree	Agree	Agree
16	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
17	Disagree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
18	Disagree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
19	Disagree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
20	Disagree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree

Part III: Challenges Encountered (Full Individual Responses)

- I find it time-consuming.
Respondent 1-10: Yes (50%) | Respondent 11-20: No (50%)
- There are no proper bins available.
Respondent 1-12: Yes (60%) | Respondent 13-20: No (40%)
- The waste collection is irregular.
Respondent 1-7: No (35%) | Respondent 8-20: Yes (65%)
- Collection schedule doesn't match.
Respondent 1-14: No (70%) | Respondent 15-20: Yes (30%)
- There is lack of awareness.
Respondent 1-9: No (45%) | Respondent 10-20: Yes (55%)